

STUDENT NURSES PERCEPTION TOWARDS CHANGING LECTURERS AND EFFECTS ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN TWO SELECTED COLLEGES OF NURSING, KOGI STATE

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Abstract: This study is based on student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers and effects on academic performance in two selected colleges of nursing, kogi state. The aim and objective of the study are all to assess student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers, to determine effect of changing lecturers towards academic performance, solutions on effects of changing lecturers towards academic performance. Chapter two considers the view of others in relation to the topic of the research while chapter three dealt with the methodology of the research. chapter three and four also dealt with research design and method used, data was collected majorly from the student nurses of the colleges through personal interaction with the permission from the colleges research committee, the questionnaires were administered personally to the various respondents from various classes in the colleges. All 226 questionnaire were administered and recovered. Data was analyzed using frequency and percentage while results were presented in tables. It was concluded that, nursing school administrators should employ the various motivational techniques in order to retain their teachers, since the effects of teachers' instability have great consequences on every aspect of the students and following recommendations to were made on how best the problem of changing lecturers can be solved in our educational system. Some of the recommendations include, good salary, motivation, and promotion among other. These will reduce the rate of continuous changing in lecturers in our educational system thereby providing quality education for the upcoming generation.

Keywords: student nurse's, academic performance, changing lecturers, educational system, upcoming generation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background to the study

In the past two decades classroom management has gone from a recognition, perennialism and punishment intervention-based paradigm to focus on pedagogy, essentialism and conventionalism through the development of classroom communities in which norms are established and academic routines promote constructive work (Nestel, et al., 2014). Early

classroom management practices included Pavlov's theories of behavior conditioning and reinforcement suggesting the elicit desirable behavior. Many new teachers find their energies focused on classroom management and discipline. According to LaPage, et al., (2005), research demonstrates that effective teaching begins with a meaningful curriculum and motivating and engaging instruction. The imperative in recent years about improving student outcomes is also about improving the quality of the teaching workforce. In recent years, however, recruiting and retaining quality teachers has become a challenge among some college of nursing especially private settings. In addition to the ageing of the teaching workforce, some countries experience high rates of attrition (changing of lecturers) among new teachers and a shortage of quality teachers in high-demand subject areas in nursing education. There is also concern about attracting high-achieving and motivated new graduate nurses into nursing educational programme, some private nursing institution lower their qualification requirements in the certification and licensing of new nursing teachers into the nursing education these have an impact on the quality of teachers employed, resulting in teaching workforce that is tasked with improving student outcomes. High changing rates of lecturers among new teachers is costly not only to nursing education but also to educational system and may prompt school authorities to fill teacher shortages by lowering qualification requirements for the certification of new teachers or by assigning teachers to teach subjects which they were not trained for. In such cases, the quality of the teaching workforce may be affected negatively (Sonia, 2020).

An ever-changing world seeks advancement in every aspect of life especially health, technology and education. Since, it is recognized that the level of education in the developed world is far higher than in the developing countries like Nigeria, it stands to reason that education has an important role to play in the evolution of developing countries. The present education system indicates that knowledge should be disseminated by the lecturers to the students. This means lecturers will select course materials, textbooks and references, design the framework of the course, conceptualize, analyze and synthesize the subject matter and present it face to face using the academic curriculum (Schweinle, et al., 2006).

Matthew, (2018) states that continuous changing lecturers affects students learning, it affects the quality of education that will be given to students, teachers need to establish a relationship with their students which involves trust, respect, and understanding of lecturers by learners. A Teacher has a direct responsibility in shaping of a student's performance generally; The teachers are a crucial and important factor in student's education and performance, teacher quality is particularly important for students with lower abilities. Today the purpose of the nursing lecturer is not just to deliver lectures and give exams, but also the nurse educator takes on the role of organizing, managing, counseling, observing and evaluating student nurses. Students were viewed as active and inactive recipients of knowledge who should always show readiness, participation and high maturity level towards academic demands for effective learning to take place (Ahmed, & Parsons, 2013).

Educational institutions are mandated to use education as a tool for social revolution and transformation. The success of a college of nursing is measured by the quality of nursing students it produces. The success of any educational institution is measured by the performance of its students in both academic and non-academic tests. This is supported by Yusuf, (2012) when contending that the performance should not only be based in terms of test and examination results and student ability to apply what is learnt and the rate at which students move on to higher learning institution, but should include other areas such as whether the students have acquired the survival skills. In spite of that, the use of students' achievement in academic work to assess the teacher's effectiveness has gained ground. The measure of academic performance as a symbol of school success can be traced way back from the Victorian period. Since then, academic performance has been used to grade schools and most importantly to determine one's career paths such as nursing profession (Bell, 2013). The 'good schools' are acclaimed to be those that are able to groom the students well enough to achieve the set standards goals especially quality nursing educational skills and clinical practice.

This is measured by use of students' academic performance both at school level and nationally. The importance of students' high performance in providing standard and quality clinical nursing care has attracted the attention of the public, policy-makers, educators, learners, ministry and international institution to employed graduate nurses. Better information about schools is also important for raising the standards (Gray, 2009). Education is a continuous process in life. It is the process of training and developing the knowledge, skill, mind and character of people. It is the process by which the latent abilities of individuals are developed that they may be useful to themselves and the society (Olaniyonu, 2018). Significant improvements in the quality of education that students receive are determined by the quality of teachers and knowledge impacted (Ewetan, & Ewetan, 2018). The issue of changing teacher as a factor that affects students' academic performance has received a lot of attention in the literature and findings have been mixed and inconclusive (Ewetan & Ewetan, 2018).

Some literature revealed that a number of teacher variables which include years of teaching experience, level of educational attainment or academic qualifications, teacher development programmes, availability of qualified teachers, teacher-student ratio, teacher attitude and degree of job satisfaction are directly and indirectly affect students' learning outcomes (Daso, 2020). Therefore, it becomes necessary to assess the student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers and effect on academic performance in two selected college of nursing, Kogi State.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The World Health Organization has recommended a skilled health worker (SHW) density of 4.45 per 1000. As at 2018, Nigeria had a SHW density of 1.83 per 1000. The factors contributing to the low density of SHWs and nursing educators include crisis in the educational sector leading to low production of an adequate health workforce, poor management/leadership within the health system, political, and economic crises leading to an increasing trend of migration of SHWs and nursing educators from Nigeria (Adeloye, et al., 2022). In 2000, an estimated 415,936 SHW migrated from low-and-middle-income countries (LMICs) to countries belonging to the Organisation for Economic Development. According to Migration Policy Institute (2021), Nigerians account for the largest African migrants 'population in the United States. Basically, the determinants of brain drain, education system are grouped into pull and push factors. Push factors which encourages health workers and qualified nursing educators to leave their country. Such factors include low wage compensation, limited educational opportunity, poor job satisfaction, political instability and under staffing.

On the contrary, pull factors attract and facilitate the movement of the teachers towards that country, such factors are career advancement, conducive working environment, autonomy, low wages and salaries and political instability. When any organization is short on staff, the consequences are immediately and tangibly felt. Operations are scaled back, hours are reduced, an increase in the clinical workload of those who choose to remain, reduction in the quality of education, negatively impacting their job satisfaction and well-being. (Olorunfemi, et al., 2020). The issue of poor academic performance of students in college of nursing has been of much concern to all and sundry. This has been attributed to so many factors such as high rate of changing lecturers from developing to developed areas and private to government institution. The rate of changing lecturers and emigration of qualified teachers in developing countries such as Nigeria has resulted to brain drain in nursing education system. This, of course will certainly have some negative effects on the students who most times take a longer period to understand the teaching methodology of the new lecturers and sometimes the new lecturer may be inexperienced and unqualified. Therefore, base on the above evidence, it is necessary to assess student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers and effect on academic performance in two selected college of nursing, Kogi State.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to determine student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers and effects on academic performance in two selected colleges of nursing, Kogi State.

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- a. To assess student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers in two selected colleges of nursing.
- b. To determine effects of changing lecturers towards academic performance in two selected colleges of nursing, Kogi State.
- c. To identify solutions on effects of changing lecturers towards academic performance in two selected colleges of nursing Kogi State.

Research Questions

1. What are student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers in two selected colleges of nursing, Kogi State?
2. What are the effects of changing lecturers towards academic performance in two selected colleges of nursing, Kogi State?
3. what are the solutions on effects of changing lecturers towards academic performance in two selected colleges of nursing Kogi State?

Significance of the Study

The outcome of this study will show the extent to which changing lecturers affects the academic performance among student nurses.

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This study will broaden the knowledge of school administrator and authorities on the retaining and maintaining qualified teachers.

The finding of this study will help to improve academic performance of student nurses by providing solution to instability of the nursing lecturers especially in private setting

The result of this study will provide framework on which state and federal government will use to provide social welfares and other benefits that help to retain qualified experienced teachers in Nigeria for effective quality standard education performance.

The outcome of this study will help to maintain, sustain and promote quality nursing education program and clinical practice in Nigeria.

This study will provide starving strategies that will ensure stability of the lecturers, not only in private college of nursing but also in private educational system

This study will add to the body of knowledge in nursing profession

Scope of the Study

This study will focus on the student nurses in two selected college of nursing which are UEC College of Nursing, Kogi State and Nana College of Nursing, Kogi State.

Definition of Terms

Academic Performance: The measurement of student achievement across various academic subjects among student nurses

Changing Lecturer: This is attrition of a person (immigration and emigration) of an academic expert who is hired to teach using the school's syllabus and curriculum on a full or part time base

College of Nursing: This is an approved and accredited institution by appropriate educational authorities to train students on practical nursing skills, knowledge, and clinical experience needed to become a registered nurse.

Effect: This is a result or consequence that occur in academic performance as a result of changing lecturers

Perception: The way changing lecturers is regarded, understood or interpreted by many student nurses.

Student Nurses: A person who is undergoing a program of basic, generalized nursing education and is not authorized by the appropriate regulatory authority to practice nursing in his or her country.

3. METHODOLOGY

A non-experimental, exploratory, descriptive study using quantitative design was adopted to determine the student nurse perception towards changing lecturers and effect on academic performance in two selected college of nursing, Kogi State. The research was carried out in selected school (UEC College of Nursing Ochadamu and Nana College of Nursing Anyigba in Kogi State).

The researcher got the total number of student Nurses from two selected College of Nursing in Kogi State. The estimated number of students Nurses within the two selected College of Nursing is 518. Taro Yamane's formula and convenience sampling technique was used to select 226 respondents. The instrument used in data collection was a well- structured questionnaire developed by the researcher to obtain data from the respondents. It was design in such a way that it provides answers to research questions. It contains four section having 26 items altogether,

Section A contains six (6) items on demographic data. Section B contains eight (7) items on student nurses' perception towards changing lecturers in two selected college of nursing, kogi state. Section C contains six (7) items on the effect of changing lecturers towards academic performance in the above selected college. Section D contains six (6) items on solutions on effects of changing lecturers towards academic performance in the above selected college. The questioner suited the objectives and research question and boxes where provided in front of each questions where respondent will tick his or her choice out of the option and all the question where close ended questions. To ensure validation of instrument use for data collection, literature study was reviewed and the questionnaire was developed based on the research objective. this

structured questionnaire was presented to the project supervisor' where correction and modification was made. Having validated the structured questionnaire prepared by the researcher, corrections were made by the project supervisor and effected before testing the reliability of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was tested using a test-retest method. Data was collected majorly from the student nurses of the colleges through personal interaction with the permission from the colleges research committee, the questionnaires were administered personally to the various respondent from various classes in the college. All the questionnaires distributed was retrieved and found suitable for entry and analysis. IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was used to analyze collected coded data, Data was analyzed using frequency and percentage while result where presented in tables. Ethical approval was obtained from the institution authority and informed consent will be signed by respondents. They were also assured that information gather will be treated confidentially and that study was purely for academic purpose and each section is relevant to the topic of the research and where expressed in simple terms.

4. RESULTS

This section deals with presentation of data and analysis of data and interpretation of data.

Data Presentation

Section A; Demographical Data

Table 1

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage%
Gender of respondents	Male	86	38.1
	Female	140	61.9
	Both	0	0
	Total	226	100
Age	15-20	76	33.6
	21-30	110	48.8
	30-40	40	17.6
	Total	226	100
Religion	Christian	160	70.8
	Islam	66	29.2
	Pegan	0	0
	Total	226	100
Marital status	Single	200	88.5
	Married	24	10.6
	Divorced	2	0.9
	Total	226	100
Educational level	Year 1	60	26.6
	Year 2	90	39.8
	Year 3	76	33.6
	Total	226	100
Ethnicity	Igbo	49	21.7
	Yoruba	40	17.7
	Hausa	15	6.6
	Others	120	53.1
	Total	226	100

Source: Field Survey 2023

The data in variable 1 shows that 86 (38.1%) of the respondents are male, 140 (61.9%) are female. It shows that most of the respondents are female.

The data in variable 2 shows that 76 (33.6%) of the respondents are 15-20 years of age, 110 (48.8%) 21-30 years and 40 (17.6%) 30-40 years of age. It shows that most of the respondents are between the age of 21-30 years.

The data in variable 3 shows that 160 (70.8%) of the respondents are Christian and 66(29.2%) are Muslim with no response in any other religion. majority is Christians.

The data in variable 4 shows that 200 (88.5%) of the respondents are single, 24(10.6%) are married and 2(0.9%) are divorced. It shows that most of the respondents are single.

The data in variable 5 shows that 60 (26.6%) of the respondents are in year 1, 90(39.8%) are in year 2 and 76(33.6%) are in year 3.the result shows that most of the respondent are in year2.

The data in variable 6 shows that 49 (21.1%) of the respondents are Igbo, 40 (17.7%) are Yoruba, 15(6.6%) are Hausa and 120(53.1%) are others. The result shows that most of the respondents are under others in college of nursing.

Table 4.2; Section B; What Are Student Nurses’ Perception Towards Changing Lecturers In Two Selected Colleges Of Nursing, Kogi State

SUBJECT	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
Changing lecturers is the immigration and emigration (attrition) of an academic expert who is hired to teach using the, different methodologies, school’s syllabus and curriculum on a full or part time base	200	26	0	0	226
Percentage %	88.5	11.5	0	0	100
Employment of a new lecturer may likely bring new technique in teaching and learning process	100	62	14	50	226
Percentage %	44.2	27.4	6.3	22.1	100
Changing lecturers usually have a significant effect on academic performance this may be direct or indirect process	26	190	0	10	226
Percentage %	11.6	88.1	0	0.3	100
Lecturer who usually leave the school within their first year of lecture maybe attributed to their personal growth and development especially financial status	180	46	0	0	226
Percentage %	79.6	20.3	0	0	100
Government employment are major reasons that nurse educators leave the private college of nursing to government setting for job security purposes	160	40	0	26	226
Percentage %	70.8	18.0	0	11.3	100
High demand of medical personnel in a developed country contributed to the emigration of those qualified lecturer for the advancement of their career	160	66	0	0	226
Percentage%	70.8	29.2	0	0	100
Introduction of new teaching techniques by newly employed nurse educator may be complex to facilitate learning process and it may take time before adjustment will take place on both teacher and students	126	100	0	0	226
Percentage%	55.8	44.2	0	0	100

Source: Field Survey 2023

The table 4.2 shows that 200(88.5%) of the respondent strongly agreed that Changing lecturers is the immigration and emigration (attrition) of an academic expert who is hired to teach using the, different methodologies, school’s syllabus and curriculum on a full or part time base and 26(11.5%) disagree.

100(44.2%) strongly agreed that employment of a new lecturer may likely bring new technique in teaching and learning process, 62(27.4%) agree to that,14(6.3%) disagree and 50(22.1%) strongly disagree.

26(11.6%) strongly agreed that changing lecturers usually have a significant effect on academic performance this may be direct or indirect process ,190 (88.1%) agreed while 10(0.3%) disagreed.

180(79.6%) strongly agreed that lecturer who usually leave the school within their first year of lecture maybe attributed to their personal growth and development especially financial status,46(20.3%) agreed while 0(0%) disagreed.

160 (70.7%) of respondent think that government employment are major reasons that nurse educators leave the private college of nursing to government setting for job security purposes ,40(18.0%) agreed and 26(11.3%) disagreed.

160(70.7%) of the respondent strongly agreed that high demand of medical personnel in a developed country contributed to the emigration of those qualified lecturer for the advancement of their career, while 66(29.2%) agreed.

126(55.8%) strongly agreed that introduction of new teaching techniques by newly employed nurse educator may be complex to facilitate learning process and it may take time before adjustment will take place on both teacher and students, while 100(44.2%) agreed.

Table 4.3; Section C; Effects of Changing Lecturers Towards Academic Performance Student Nurses

SUBJECT	RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE%
Do you think changing lecturers can affect academic activities in the college of nursing which may result to poor academic performance among nursing student	Yes	166	73.4
	No	60	26.6
	Total	226	100
Does untimely leaving of lecturers in private college of nursing affect academic calendar and educational structure of the college	Yes	160	70.8
	No	66	29.2
	Total	226	100
Does lecturer who leave within first year of their employment cause brain drain in college of nursing	Yes	126	55.8
	No	100	44.2
	Total	226	100
Does changing lecturers affect the emotion and relationship between the lecturer and the student that leads to disrupt personality development of the students	Yes	166	73.4
	No	60	26.6
	Total	226	100
Does emigration of the lecturers result into many lecturers to take one course or topic in different dimensions which may obstruct and hinder learning process	Yes	166	73.4
	No	60	26.6
	Total	226	100
Emigration of lecturers in private college of nursing reduce the number of lecturers leaving students to adopt student centered method which may not really help in academic and clinical practice	Yes	186	82.3
	No	40	17.7
	Total	226	100

Source; Field Survey 2023

The table 4.2shows that 166(73.4%) of the respondent agreed that changing lecturers can affect academic activities in the college of nursing which may result to poor academic performance among nursing student while 60(26.6%) of the respondent disagreed. The result shows that most of the most respondent shows that changing lecturers can affect academic activities in the college of nursing which may result to poor academic performance.

160(70.8%) agreed that untimely leaving of lecturers in private college of nursing affect academic calendar and educational structure of the college while 66(29.2%) disagreed.

126(55.8%) agreed that lecturer who leave within first year of their employment cause brain drain in college of nursing, and 100(44.2%) disagreed. The result shows that most of the respondents agreed lecturer who leave within first year of their employment cause brain drain in college of nursing.

166(73.4%) agreed that changing lecturers affect the emotion and relationship between the lecturer and the student that leads to disrupt personality development of the students and 60(26.6%) disagreed. The result shows that most of the respondents answered agreed that changing lecturers affect the emotion and relationship between the lecturer and the student that leads to disrupt personality development of the students.

166(73.4%) agreed emigration of the lecturers result into many lecturers to take one course or topic in different dimensions which may obstruct and hinder learning process that while 60(26.6%) disagreed.

186(82.3%) emigration of lecturers in private college of nursing reduce the number of lecturers leaving students to adopt student centered method which may not really help in academic and clinical practice while 60(26.6%) disagreed.

Table 4.4; Section D; Solutions on Effects of Changing Lecturers Towards Academic Performance Tick Possible Solution on Changing Lecturers.

SUBJECT	RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Can changing lecturer be solved by good leadership and administrative support	Yes	224	99.1
	No	2	0.9
	Total	226	100
Provision of well-ventilated academic setting with good welfare package can help to retain qualified lecturers in the private college of nursing	Yes	226	100
	No	0	0
	Total	226	100
Bilateral conversion and implementation of the federal government salaries may help young lecturers that are newly qualified to stay for long period in private college of nursing	Yes	226	100
	No	0	0
	Total	226	100
Encouragement of academic progression by sponsors and indirect sponsors through loan may motivate newly qualified lecturers to stay in the private college of nursing	Yes	226	100
	No	0	0
	Total	226	100
Siting of college of nursing in a city rather than rural or underdeveloped area may promote stability of lecturers in the private college of nursing	Yes	226	100
	No	0	0
	Total	226	226
Retaining of new qualified teachers may help in promotion of teacher stability	Yes	222	98.2
	No	4	1.8
	Total	226	100

Source: Field Survey 2023

The table 4.4 shows that 224(99.1%) of the respondent agreed that changing lecturer be solved by good leadership and administrative support and 2(0.9%) disagree.

226(100%) agree that provision of well-ventilated academic setting with good welfare package can help to retain qualified lecturers in the private college of nursing.

226(100%) agreed that bilateral conversion and implementation of the federal government salaries may help young lecturers that are newly qualified to stay for long period in private college of nursing.

226(100%) agreed that encouragement of academic progression by sponsors and indirect sponsors through loan may motivate newly qualified lecturers to stay in the private college of nursing.

226(100%) agreed that siting of college of nursing in a city rather than rural or underdeveloped area may promote stability of lecturers in the private college of nursing.

226(100%) agreed that Retaining of new qualified teachers may help in promotion of teacher stability.

Summary of the Major Finding.

Two hundred and twenty-six 226(100%) respondents answered the question from the data analyzed, it shows that most of the respondents were female between the age of 21-30 years, 160 (70.8%) of the respondents were Christian, 200 (88.5%) of the respondents were single, 190(39.8%) were in year 2. The data in variable 6 shows that 49 (21.1%) of the respondents are Igbo, 40 (17.7%) are Yoruba, 15(6.6%) are Hausa and 120(53.1%) are others. The result shows that most of the respondents are under others in college of nursing.

The table 4.2 shows that 200(88.5%) of the respondent strongly agreed that Changing lecturers is the immigration and emigration (attrition) of an academic expert who is hired to teach using: different methodologies, school’s syllabus and curriculum on a full or part time base and 26(11.5%) disagree. 100(44.2%) strongly agree that employment of a new lecturer may likely bring new technique in teaching and learning process, 62(27.4%) agree to that, 14(6.3%) disagree and 50(22.1%) strongly disagree. 26(11.6%) strongly agreed that changing lecturers usually have a significant effect on academic performance this may be direct or indirect process ,190 (88.1%) agreed while 10(0.3%) disagreed. 180(79.6%) strongly agreed that lecturer who usually leave the school within their first year of lecture maybe attributed to their personal growth and development especially financial status,46(20.3%) agreed while 0(0%) disagreed. 160 (70.7%) of respondent think that government employment are major reasons that nurse educators leave the private college of nursing to government setting

for job security purposes ,40(18.0%) agreed and 26(11.3%) disagreed. 160(70.7%) of the respondent strongly agreed that high demand of medical personnel in a developed country contributed to the emigration of those qualified lecturer for the advancement of their career, while 66(29.2%) agreed. 126(55.8%) strongly agreed that introduction of new teaching techniques by newly employed nurse educator may be complex to facilitate learning process and it may take time before adjustment will take place on both teacher and students, while 100(44.2%) agreed.

The table 4.3 shows that 166(73.4%) of the respondent agreed that changing lecturers can affect academic activities in the college of nursing which may result to poor academic performance among nursing student while 60(26.6%) of the respondent disagreed. 160(70.8%) agreed that untimely leaving of lecturers in private college of nursing affect academic calendar and educational structure of the college while 66(29.2%) disagreed. 126(55.8%) agreed that lecturer who leave within first year of their employment cause brain drain in college of nursing, and 100(44.2%) disagreed. 166(73.4%) agreed that changing lecturers affect the emotion and relationship between the lecturer and the student that leads to disrupt personality development of the students and 60(26.6%) disagreed. 166(73.4%) agreed emigration of the lecturers result into many lecturers to take one course or topic in different dimensions which may obstruct and hinder learning process that while 60(26.6%) disagreed. 186(82.3%) emigration of lecturers in private college of nursing reduce the number of lecturers leaving students to adopt student centered method which may not really help in academic and clinical practice while 60(26.6%) disagreed.

The table 4.4 shows that 224(99.1%) of the respondent agreed that changing lecturer be solved by good leadership and administrative support and 2(0.9%) disagree. 226(100%) agree that provision of well-ventilated academic setting with good welfare package can help to retain qualified lecturers in the private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that bilateral conversion and implementation of the federal government salaries may help young lecturers that are newly qualified to stay for long period in private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that encouragement of academic progression by sponsors and indirect sponsors through loan may motivate newly qualified lecturers to stay in the private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that siting of college of nursing in a city rather than rural or underdeveloped area may promote stability of lecturers in the private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that Retaining of new qualified teachers may help in promotion of teacher stability.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section summarizes the discussion of findings, show the relationship of the research to other studies and the implication to nursing. It also summarizes the whole chapter showing the conclusion and recommendations.

Discussion of the Research Findings

Research Question 1

Student Nurse's Perception towards Changing Lecturers

According the study it was observe that 200(88.5%) of the respondent strongly agreed that Changing lecturers is the immigration and emigration (attrition) of an academic expert who is hired to teach using the, different methodologies, school's syllabus and curriculum on a full or part time base and 26(11.5%) disagree. 100(44.2%) strongly agree that employment of a new lecturer may likely bring new technique in teaching and learning process, 62(27.4%) agree to that,14(6.3%) disagree and 50(22.1%) strongly disagree. 26(11.6%) strongly agreed that changing lecturers usually have a significant effect on academic performance this may be direct or indirect process ,190 (88.1%) agreed while 10(0.3%) disagreed. 180(79.6%) strongly agreed that lecturer who usually leave the school within their first year of lecture maybe attributed to their personal growth and development especially financial status,46(20.3%) agreed while 0(0%) disagreed. 160 (70.7%) of respondent think that government employment are major reasons that nurse educators leave the private college of nursing to government setting for job security purposes ,40(18.0%) agreed and 26(11.3%) disagreed. 160(70.7%) of the respondent strongly agreed that high demand of medical personnel in a developed country contributed to the emigration of those qualified lecturer for the advancement of their career, while 66(29.2%) agreed.126(55.8%) strongly agreed that introduction of new teaching techniques by newly employed nurse educator may be complex to facilitate learning process and it may take time before adjustment will take place on both teacher and students, while 100(44.2%) agreed.

This study is similar to that of Qualters (2021) on students' perceptions towards changing lecturer was compared to teaching methods that require students to learn actively, the study suggested that students do not favor continuous changing lecturer

because of the in-class time taken by the activities, fear of not covering all of the material in the course, and anxiety about changing from lecturers frequently. Casado (2020) examined students' perceptions across six teaching methods: lecture/discussion, lab work, in-class exercises, guest speakers, applied projects, and oral presentations. A study conducted by Canter & Gallatin (2018) on student behavior in relation to changing lecturers, found a noticeable difference between students' attitude and behavior indicating a preference for discussions to lectures, however, when given the opportunity actually preferred the lecture to the discussion.

Research Question 2

Effects of Changing Lecturers towards Academic Performance Student Nurse's Perception towards Changing Lecturers

According to this study it was observed that 166(73.4%) of the respondent agreed that changing lecturers can affect academic activities in the college of nursing which may result to poor academic performance among nursing student while 60(26.6%) of the respondent disagreed. 160(70.8%) agreed that untimely leaving of lecturers in private college of nursing affect academic calendar and educational structure of the college while 66(29.2%) disagreed. 126(55.8%) agreed that lecturer who leave within first year of their employment cause brain drain in college of nursing, and 100(44.2%) disagreed. 166(73.4%) agreed that changing lecturers affect the emotion and relationship between the lecturer and the student that leads to disrupt personality development of the students and 60(26.6%) disagreed. 166(73.4%) agreed emigration of the lecturers result into many lecturers to take one course or topic in different dimensions which may obstruct and hinder learning process that while 60(26.6%) disagreed. 186(82.3%) emigration of lecturers in private college of nursing reduce the number of lecturers leaving students to adopt student centered method which may not really help in academic and clinical practice while 60(26.6%) disagreed.

A similar study was carried out by Abdullahi (2020) who stated that there are links between student performance and the stability of the lecturer. students who have established a good relationship and trust in a lecturer, his sudden absence affects the psychology of the students who may take a longer time to understand the teaching methodology of the new lecturer and build a new relationship and trust in the new lecturer. A considerable research has been made on the effects of lecturers change on the performance of students. Promise (2018), stated that the influence of lecturers teaching effectiveness on the learning outcome of the learners depends on the stability of the lecturer. A research carried out by Adewara (2020), indicates that effective teaching which depends on lecturer's stability and is a significant predictor to student's performance.

Research Question 3

Solutions on Effects of Changing Lecturers towards Academic Performance

that 224(99.1%) of the respondent agreed that changing lecturer be solved by good leadership and administrative support and 2(0.9%) disagree. 226(100%) agree that provision of well-ventilated academic setting with good welfare package can help to retain qualified lecturers in the private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that bilateral conversion and implementation of the federal government salaries may help young lecturers that are newly qualified to stay for long period in private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that encouragement of academic progression by sponsors and indirect sponsors through loan may motivate newly qualified lecturers to stay in the private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that siting of college of nursing in a city rather than rural or underdeveloped area may promote stability of lecturers in the private college of nursing. 226(100%) agreed that Retaining of new qualified teachers may help in promotion of teacher stability.

This similar study was carried out by Maganga, J.H., (2020), the study focused on the factors that affect changing lecturers towards academic performance and possible solution in secondary schools in Ilala district. The study employed qualitative research design. Interview, focused group discussion and documentary were employed in data collection. The findings revealed that many learners could not master the English as (LOI), and they had very poor knowledge of vocabularies used in various subjects. Further, the results showed that with exception of non-qualified staff, enough teacher were not enough due to changing qualified teachers in Ilala Secondary Schools. This limited effective learning of various discipline like Physics. The funding further indicated that the schools were experiencing problems of science on one side

Limitations of the Study

The demanding schedule of respondents made it very difficult getting the respondents to participate in the survey. As a result, retrieving copies of questionnaire in timely fashion was very challenging. Also, the researcher is a student and therefore has limited time as well as resources in covering extensive literature available in conducting this research.

Implications of Findings to Nursing/Midwifery

The nursing implication of this study is that project development content prepares students to conduct rigorous usability testing, provide appropriate system training and adopt quality improvement models to evaluate the effectiveness and accuracy of automated system and emphasis on communication, information needs. The school should work together to provide possible solution to the continuous changing in lecturers

Summary of the Study

This study investigated the perception of student nurses towards nursing informatics in two selected college of nursing in Kogi state. Chapter one deals with introduction of the topic, objective of the study, significance of the study, statement of the problem, research question, scope of the study, limitation and operational terms were used in this research, chapter two looks at the view of others in relation to the topic of the research, chapter three dealt with the methodology of the research and chapter 4 dealt with data analysis. The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. A sample of 226 respondents was selected from a population of 518 using convenience sampling techniques where the researchers use personal decision to determine the members of the population that is convenient and accessible. The method of data collection was questionnaire which were distributed and all returned. Data obtained was analyzed using frequency tables and percentage.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, based on the observation of the effect of changing lecturers on academic performance, schools administrators should employ the various motivational techniques in order to retain their teachers. Since the effects of teachers' instability have great consequences on every aspects of the students. Teachers on the other hand, should develop more interest in their job and see it as a profession so as to be more committed and stable in their duty post. The study adopted a descriptive study non-experimental design to assess student nurse's perception towards changing lecturers and effect on academic performance in two selected college of nursing, Kogi State. Data was collected majorly from the student nurses of the colleges through personal interaction with the permission from the colleges research committee, the questionnaires were administered personally to the various respondent from various classes in the college. All 226 questionnaire were administered and recovered. Data were collected and analyzed, summary and recommendation were presented.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

Nursing Education and Practice

In order to remedy the problems faced in our schools as a result of changing of lecturers, it is necessary to take a critical look at how best the issues discussed would be handled to enhance better performance of student and to encourage teachers to remain at their duty post. Emphasis should be placed on the following to enable teachers to be stable and to be more effective in their service.

- a. *Enhanced motivation for teachers:* Teachers should be motivated by early payment of salaries, recognition and other incentives that will encourage them to stay.
- b. *Better salary:* Private schools should endeavor to make teachers feel comfortable by paying good salary. This will encourage teachers to stay.
- c. *Enhanced Administrative support:* Administrators should foster a sense of belonging and by involving teachers in decision making. This makes them feel important.
- d. *Promotion of teachers:* Teachers should be promoted at the right time. This will energize them to invest more in the lives and education of the learners. When teachers are promoted at the right time, they feel motivated to put in their best.
- e. *Teachers training:* Training of teachers is one of the keys to retaining teachers therefore, administrators are to support and encourage teachers to improve and update their knowledge. This can be done through seminars, workshops and conferences
- f. *Teachers' compensation:* The issue of compensation can never be over emphasized in retaining teachers. Teachers should be encouraged at the end of each term by the administrators for their efforts and work. This can be done by giving them gifts, this will go a long way to encourage them to stay and remain committed to their work.

Suggestions for Further Studies

This study serves as a basis for further research study on student nurses' perception towards changing lecturers and effect on academic performance, the researcher suggests that this study should be conducted in other colleges of nursing.

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APPENDIX
QUESTIONNAIRE
STUDENT NURSES PERCEPTION TOWARDS CHANGING LECTURERS AND EFFECT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN TWO SELECTED COLLEGE OF NURSING IN KOGI STATE

The purpose of the questionnaire is for you to supply all necessary information required to complete my research work. This research work is purely academic purpose and your response will be treated confidential.

Thanks for your cooperation

INSTRUCTION: Please the following statements carefully and tick the box that best suit your opinion

SECTION A; DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1. Sex: (a) male () (b) female () (c) Both ()
2. Age: (a)15-20 () (b) 21-30 () (c) 30-40 ()

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3. Religion: (a) Christian () (b) Islam () (c) pegan
4. Marital status (a) single () (b) married () (c) Divorce ()
5. Education level (a) year 1 () (b) year 2 () (c) year 3 ()
6. Ethnicity (a) Igbo () (b) Yoruba () (c) Hausa () (d) Others ()

SECTION B: What are student nurses' perception towards changing lecturers in two selected college of nursing, Kogi state

Items	SA	A	D	SD
Changing lecturers is the immigration and emigration (attrition) of an academic expert who is hired to teach using the, different methodologies, school's syllabus and curriculum on a full or part time base				
Employment of a new lecturer may likely bring new technique in teaching and learning process				
Changing lecturers usually have a significant effect on academic performance this may be direct or indirect process				
Lecturer who usually leave the school within their first year of lecture maybe attributed to their personal growth and development especially financial status				
Government employment are major reasons that nurse educators leave the private college of nursing to government setting for job security purposes				
High demand of medical personnel in a developed country contributed to the emigration of those qualified lecturer for the advancement of their career				
Introduction of new teaching techniques by newly employed nurse educator may be complex to facilitate learning process and it may take time before adjustment will take place on both teacher and students				

SECTION C: effect of changing lecturers towards academic performance

SUBJECT	YES	N O
Do you think changing lecturers can affect academic activities in the college of nursing which may result to poor academic performance among nursing student		
Does untimely leaving of lecturers in private college of nursing affect academic calendar and educational structure of the college		
Does lecturer who leave within first year of their employment cause brain drain in college of nursing		
Does changing lecturers affect the emotion and relationship between the lecturer and the student that leads to disrupt personality development of the students		
Does emigration of the lecturers result into many lecturers to take one course or topic in different dimensions which may obstruct and hinder learning process		
Emigration of lecturers in private college of nursing reduce the number of lecturers leaving students to adopt student centered method which may not really help in academic and clinical practice		

SECTION D: solutions on effects of changing lecturers towards academic performance Tick possible solution to changing lecturers.

SUBJECT	YES	NO
Can changing lecturer be solved by good leadership and administrative support		
Provision of well-ventilated academic setting with good welfare package can help to retain qualified lecturers in the private college of nursing		
Bilateral conversion and implementation of the federal government salaries may help young lecturers that are newly qualified to stay for long period in private college of nursing		
Encouragement of academic progression by sponsors and indirect sponsors through loan may motivate newly qualified lecturers to stay in the private college of nursing		
Siting of college of nursing in a city rather than rural or underdeveloped area may promote stability of lecturers in the private college of nursing		
Retaining of new qualified teachers may help in promotion of teacher stability		